

WOOD STOCK

Inventory report

Deliverable 3.1

Standing forest, forest products, by-products, and post-consumer wood

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1. Preface

The WoodStock project is focusing on four underutilised wood stocks: hardwood, low-quality wood, damaged wood, and post-consumer and residual wood. The objective of this report is to provide background information on the forest value chain in Europe. It provides information on the flow of materials throughout the entire forest product value chain, serving as a baseline for the current status. From the data, substantial quantitative data can be derived about hardwoods and post-consumer wood. Some information is available on by-products (residual wood), while little quantitative data is available on the volumes of damaged and low-quality wood.

The data in this report are mainly collected from Eurostat and FAO. The advantage of using European databases over national sources is that they provide harmonised data across all countries, enabling direct and reliable comparisons. The data gathered in the report supports the Material Flow Analysis (MFA) model in the WoodStock project.

This report is closely linked to the following WoodStock reports:

- O'Hagan & Brancart (2025) 'Review of new technologies and processes', D5.1.
Through case studies and literature review, the report identifies the most prominent technologies, groups them by application area, and illustrates how they can support greater use of underutilised wood resources to reduce waste.
- Nanda & Hughes (2025) 'Characteristics of underutilised wood stock', D5.2.
The report defines, identifies, characterises and derives potential applications for underutilised wood stocks in the EU, focusing on four underutilised wood stocks: hardwood, low-quality wood, damaged wood, and post-consumer and residual wood.
- Zdziarska, De Ligne & Baño (2025) 'Review of zero-waste product concepts', D5.3.
The report seeks to address the following questions:
 - What can we do with underutilised wood resources? - identifying potential applications.
 - How can we get there? - formulating design strategies used to develop building components from non-standard wood.
 - What is the socio-cultural and environmental impact of design strategies used to develop building products from underutilised wood streams? - evaluating the sustainability potential and socio-cultural implications.
- Gedde (2026) 'Material Intensities in the building stock', D3.2.
The report explores material intensities for wood from Europe on an element and building scale.
- Cord'homme et al. (2026) 'Quasi-stationary MFA model', D3.3.
An approach to facilitate MFA of wood is developed and quantified for three case countries.

2. Introduction

It is important to understand existing resources to identify potential underutilised ones. This report provides an overview of the standing forest in Europe, its environmental functions, roundwood removals, wood products, forestry economic aggregates, post-consumer wood, and wood stored in the building stock.

To represent the diversity in Europe, case countries from eastern, western, northern, and southern Europe were selected. The countries differ in geographical location and size, forest cover, population size, and in how they have traditionally utilised wood resources. In

northern Europe, Norway and Finland were included, in western Europe, Ireland and France, in eastern Europe, Poland, and in southern Europe, Slovenia (Figure 1). Finland and Norway are part of the boreal forest belt. Finland and Slovenia have among the highest forest shares in Europe. Finland and Norway are characterised by large, continuous forest landscapes, mostly coniferous or mixed mountain forests. Slovenia has mixed forests, but coniferous forests in the mountains. France and Poland have large temperate mixed-forest countries. Ireland has the lowest forest cover of the case countries. Its forests are mainly planted and relatively young compared to those in continental Europe.

Figure 1: Regions and case countries.

3. Forest

Europe’s forest resources represent a fundamental component of the continent’s natural capital, providing the biological basis for timber supply, carbon storage, biodiversity, and a wide range of ecosystem services.

Forest Europe (2026) provides an overview of the state of Europe’s forests, a short summary below:

Forest area: Around 43% of Europe’s forests are predominantly coniferous, about 40% are broadleaved, and the remainder are mixed, with substantial regional variation. Overall, the share of broadleaved forest has increased over the past five years.

Growing stock: Europe's forests contain about 38 300 million m³ of growing stock, around 79% of which is in forests available for wood supply. While growing stock increased by nearly 1.3% annually over the past 30 years, growth slowed to about 0.3% in the last five years due to reduced forest expansion, ageing stands, higher utilisation, and forest damage.

Net annual increment: Wood use in European forests remains sustainable, with fellings at about 81% of net annual increment. Since 1990, both growth and harvest have increased, especially in Northern and Central-West Europe. Higher cuttings partly reflect salvage logging and stand regeneration in some regions.

Species composition: European forests have become more diverse in recent years, with mixed-species stands covering nearly 70% of the forest area. About 30% of forests remain single-species, mainly softwood, reflecting natural growing conditions.

Introduced species: Introduced tree species cover about 4% of Europe's forests but can be regionally important. Their future role may be reconsidered for climate adaptation, depending on site suitability and risks such as invasiveness and biodiversity impacts.

Natural and semi-natural forest: Most European forests are semi-natural (95%), with plantations and undisturbed forests each covering about 2-3%. All forest types have expanded since 1990, reflecting overall forest area growth.

Roundwood production: Roundwood production remains Europe's main forestry activity at about 626 million m³ per year. Northern and Central Europe dominate production, with Sweden, Finland, Germany, France, and Poland accounting for half of the total.

Forest damage: European forests are damaged by fire, storms, pests, wildlife, and grazing. Climate change is intensifying these impacts, with fires dominating in the Mediterranean and storms and insects in Central Europe. Damage reporting remains uneven, though improvements are underway.

Protected forest: In 2025, protected forests covered 26% of the forest area in reporting countries. About 17% are protected mainly for biodiversity and 10% for landscape conservation and specific natural features. Protected forest areas have steadily increased over the past 25 years, though growth has slowed in recent years.

Non-wood goods: Non-wood goods and forest services provide important ecosystem services and income in Europe. Plant products dominate marketed non-wood goods, while nature-related services dominate forest services. Valuation remains inconsistent across countries, but reported values are substantial.

Recreation: Around 65% of Europe's forests are available for public recreation, exceeding 90% in most countries. Only about 4% are primarily designated for recreation, and overall availability has changed little.

WoodStock focuses on hardwood, low-quality, damaged, and post-consumer wood. These categories differ widely in volume and in how well they are captured by databases and surveys. Hardwood is reported separately for roundwood and some of the semi-finished categories. Data on post-consumer wood are improving, while low-quality and damaged wood remain difficult to quantify.

Monitoring forest resources is essential for assessing the sustainability of forest use, understanding regional differences in forest productivity, and informing policy decisions on forest management, climate action, and resource governance across Europe.

Following harvest, timber enters several processing pathways (Figure 2). The raw material is typically delivered to sawmills, panel industries, or pulp and paper mills, where it is converted into semi-finished products such as sawnwood, wood-based panels, and paper or paperboard. These processes also generate significant volumes of by-products, including chips, sawdust, shavings, bark, and black liquor. Currently, most by-products are used for

energy recovery (incineration), but some are used for gardening or farm applications. The range of final wood products is extensive, and their service lifetimes vary considerably, from less than one year for household paper products to several decades for structural timber used in construction. At the end of life, post-consumer wood can be incinerated, with or without energy recovery, or sent to material recovery. Potential uses for the latter include reuse, remanufacturing, repurposing, and recycling.

Figure 2: Wood material flows along the forest value chain. Adapted from Giuntoli et al. (2022).

Figure 2 illustrates an overview of material flows along the forest value chain, from harvest to semi-finished products. A more detailed description of the individual product categories is provided in Table 1, based on the Joint Forest Sector Questionnaire (JFSQ) classification of primary products (JFSQ, 2023), while Table 2 presents the classification of secondary-processed wood and paper products. Hence, the JFSQ differentiates between primary forest products and secondary-processed wood products, with the latter representing more highly processed, near-final products further downstream in the wood value chain. Together, these tables support the identification of use areas for different product categories within the WoodStock project. Data on engineered wood products (e.g. CLT, LVL, glulam) are currently not available in the JFSQ. Although these product categories were officially added in 2022, reporting has not yet been implemented (UNECE & FAO, 2023).

The JFSQ classification framework is also applied in the FAOSTAT and Eurostat databases, which provide annual data at the global and European levels, respectively.

Table 1: Joint Forest Sector Questionnaire (JFSQ) classification of forest products (JQ1 Production). Category 1 is roundwood removals, categories 2-12 are production. C = coniferous wood species, NC = non-coniferous wood species (i.e. hardwood species), NC.T = Tropical wood species. Source: Joint Forest Sector Questionnaire - Form: JQ1 Removals (JFSQ 2023).

Category	Subcategory	Detailed item
1. Roundwood (wood in the rough)	1.1. Wood fuel (incl. wood for charcoal) 1.1.C, 1.1.NC	
	1.2. Industrial roundwood 1.2.C, 1.2.NC, 1.2.NC.T	1.2.1 Sawnlogs and veneer logs 1.2.1.C, 1.2.1.NC
		1.2.2 Pulpwood round and split (incl. wood for particle board, OSB and fibreboard) 1.2.2.C, 1.2.2.NC
		1.2.3 Other industrial roundwood 1.2.3.C, 1.2.3.NC
2. Wood charcoal		
3. Wood chips, particles, and residues	3.1 Wood chips and particles	
	3.2. Wood residues (incl. wood for agglomerates)	3.2.1 Sawdust
4. Recovered post-consumer wood		
5. Wood pellets and other agglomerates	5.1. Wood pellets	
	5.2. Other agglomerates	
6. Sawnwood (incl. sleepers) 6.C, 6.NC, 6.NC.T		
7. Veneer sheets 7.C, 7.NC, 7.NC.T		
8. Wood-based panels	8.1 Plywood 8.1.C, 8.1.NC, 8.1.NC.T	
	8.2 Particle board, oriented strand board (OSB) and similar board	8.2.1 oriented strand board (OSB)
	8.3 Fibreboard	8.3.1 Hardboard
		8.3.2 Medium/High-density fibreboard (MDF/HDF)
8.3.3 Other fibreboard		
9. Wood pulp	9.1 Mechanical and semi-chemical wood pulp	
	9.2 Chemical wood pulp	9.2.1 Sulphate pulp
		9.2.2 Sulphite Pulp
9.3 Dissolving grades		
10. Other pulp	10.1 Pulp from fibres other than wood	
	10.2 Recovered fibre pulp	
11. Recovered paper		
12. Paper and paperboard	12.1 Graphic papers	5 detailed items (not listed)
	12.2 Household and sanitary papers	
	12.3 Packaging materials	
	12.4 Other paper and paperboard	

Table 2: Joint Forest Sector Questionnaire (JFSQ) classification of secondary processed wood and paper products (JQ3). C = coniferous wood species, NC = non-coniferous wood species (i.e. hardwood species), NC.T = Tropical wood species. Source: Joint Forest Sector Questionnaire - Form: JQ3 Secondary processed wood and paper products (JFSQ 2023).

Category	Subcategory	Detailed item
13. Secondary wood products	13.1 Further processed sawnwood 13.1.C, 13.1.NC, 13.1.NC.T	
	13.2 Wooden wrapping and packing material	
	13.3 Wood products for domestic/decorative use	
	13.4 Builder's joinery and carpentry of wood	
	13.5 Wooden furniture	
	13.6 Prefabricated buildings of wood	
	13.7 Other manufactured wood products	
14. Secondary paper products	14.1 Composite paper and paperboard	
	14.2 Special coated paper	
	14.3 Household and sanitary paper, ready for use	
	14.4 Packaging cartons, boxes, etc.	
	14.5 Other articles of paper or paperboard	3 detailed items (not listed)

Table 3 lists different steps in the forest-based value chain and potential causes of damage. The product categories follow the JFSQ system given in Table 1, and definitions and volumes for the main categories are given in section 3.4.

Table 3: Classification of the forest value chain based on IPCC (2019) and FAO forest products definitions (JFSQ 2023). In addition, the potential causes of damage at each step are listed.

Value chain stage	Value chain		Causes of potential damage
Forest	Standing trees		Potential damage caused by e.g. fungi, insects, fire, drought, floods, avalanches
Harvest	Roundwood		
Processing	Industrial roundwood		Potential damage during transport and storage
	Sawnlogs and veneer logs	Sawnwood	
		Wood-based panels	
	Pulpwood, round and split	Wood pulp	
		Paper and paperboard	
	Other industrial roundwood		
	Fuelwood		
	Energy wood (industrial)		
	Firewood (households)		
	Recovered paper		

Table 4 lists 1) main product categories, 2) their subcategories, 3) by-products, 4) current use areas for by-products and 5) potential future use areas for by-products. This table, in combination with Table 4 is one piece in the puzzle of mapping where and why wood becomes underutilised across the value chain and links each by-product to its current and potential higher-value uses. Regarding potential future use areas a few keywords are added in Table 3. For more information about potential future use areas, we refer to the following WoodStock reports: O’Hagan & Brancart (2025) ‘Review of new technologies and processes’, D5.1, Nanda & Hughes (2025) ‘Characteristics of underutilised wood stock’, D5.2, and Zdziarska, De Ligne & Baño (2025) ‘Review of zero-waste product concepts’, D5.3.

Table 4: By-products from the forest value chain, their current and potential future use areas.

Main categories	Sub-categories	By-products	Current use areas for by-products	Examples of potential future use areas for by-products
Standing tree		Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
Roundwood		Small-diameter logs from thinning	Left in the forest or energy	Local and niche use, like fencing and landscape elements
		Branches and tops	Mainly left in the forest, and sometimes, for energy recovery. WP5: furniture, interior panels	Biochemicals, biocarbon, fences. WP5: Furniture, building components (e.g. trusses, space frames, connectors, rainscreen cladding), wood-based panels
		Stumps and roots	Mainly left in the forest, and sometimes, for energy recovery.	Biochemicals, biocarbon, biochar
		Whole tree chips	Energy recovery, no by-products	Biochemicals, biocarbon
Industrial roundwood	Sawnlogs and veneer logs	Bark	Biofuel for own heat production, mulching, and a small portion as an oil absorbent. Biocarbon is used in the silicon industry as a reductant. WP5: Some examples of bark as exterior building cladding exist	Biochemicals, biocarbon WP5: Wood-based panels, insulation, interior decorative panels, cladding
		Wood fines	Wood-based panels, animal bedding (often mixed with planer shavings), pellet production, and blending into own fuel. Biocarbon is used in the silicon industry as a reductant.	Biochemicals, biocarbon
		Dry offcut	Mostly in wood-based panels, some use energy wood in their own facility. Block floors, interior panels	Biochemicals, biocarbon, biochar WP5: Stackable modular building blocks, trusses
		Moist offcut	Further processed into pulpwood chips.	Biochemicals, biocarbon, biochar
		Pulpwood chips	Mostly used in the pulp and paper industry, but also for wood-based panels. Biocarbon is used in the silicon industry as a reductant	Biochemicals, biocarbon, biochar
		Shavings	Raw material for wood-based panels, animal bedding, pellets/briquettes, and own fuel. Biocarbon is used in the silicon industry as a reductant	Biochemicals, biocarbon
	Wood-based panels	Sanding dust	Internal reuse (milled and back in the process)	Current use of by-products is efficient
		Offcuts	Internal reuse (milled and back in the process)	Current use of by-products is efficient
		Wood fines	Internal reuse	Current use of by-products is efficient

Paper and paperboard	Bark	Energy recovery	Biochemicals, biocarbon WP5: Wood-based panels, insulation, interior decorative panels, cladding	
	Wood fines	Used internally and/or for energy recovery	Biochemicals, biocarbon	
	Black liquor	Burned in recovery boilers to generate steam and electricity for pulp mills	Biorefinery	
	Sludge	Composting or land application as a soil amendment, energy recovery,	Biorefinery	
	Lignin	Mostly combusted for energy.	Biorefinery, chemicals, adhesives and binders, material polymers, agriculture and soil applications	
	Tall oil	Biofuels, rosin, turpentine, adhesives, paint, ink and wellness products.	Biorefinery	
	Turpentine	Solvents, fragrances and flavouring agents, chemical feedstock for resins and synthetic camphor	Biorefinery	
Fuel wood	Energy wood (industrial)	None	Energy recovery and no by-products	Energy wood could be used for products rather than energy: Biochemicals, biocarbon WP5: Solid timber beams and boards, glulam, structural composite lumber, window frames and doors, wood-based panels, cladding, flooring
	Firewood (households)	None	Energy recovery and no by-products	Firewood could be used for products rather than energy:
Recovered paper			Reused in paper or paperboard	
Recovered wood packaging				WP5: Particle boards, CLT form pallets

3.1. Forest resources

Area of wooded land

Wooded land covers a substantial share of Europe’s land surface. But the distribution varies considerably across Europe, influenced by geography, population density, long-term land-use patterns, historical forest management practices and natural growing conditions. Monitoring changes of wooded land provides important information on forest expansion or loss and supports assessments of biodiversity, carbon dynamics and sustainable land management at the European scale.

FAO (2026) uses the following definitions for ‘forest’ and ‘other wooded land’:

“Forests are lands of more than 0.5 hectares, with a tree canopy cover of more than 10 percent, which are not primarily under agricultural or urban land use.”

“Other wooded land is land with a canopy cover of 5-10 percent of trees able to reach a height of 5 m in situ; or a canopy cover of more than 10 percent when smaller trees, shrubs and bushes are included.”

The area of wooded land in forests measured in thousand hectares (Figure 3A) is quite stable in all countries except France, where there is a slight increase. The highest area is found in Finland, followed by France, Norway and Poland. Slovenia and Ireland have less than 1 300 kha of wooded land.

The area of other wooded land (Figure 3B) is quite stable in all countries, highest in Norway, followed by very similar areas in France and Finland. In Slovenia and Ireland, around 100 kha

or less is recorded for other wooded land, whereas 0 is recorded in the Eurostat database for Poland for all years. Note that in Eurostat datasets, zero values may represent either true zeros or missing data, depending on accompanying data flags. No such flags were identified for this dataset. Given that it is implausible for Poland to have no forest on other wooded land, the zero value is therefore interpreted as indicating missing data rather than a true zero. It is also important to note that data may be available from other sources.

Figure 3: Area of wooded land, in thousand hectares, 1990-2025. A: forest, B: other wooded land. Please note the different scale on the y-axis in A and B. Source: Eurostat - Area of wooded land (FAO) [for_area] (Eurostat 2026).

Forest area as a percent of land area shows how dominant forests are in a country’s landscape and is crucial for understanding ecological influence, land-use patterns, and the capacity to deliver ecosystem services. In contrast, absolute forest area (Figure 3) measures the total forest resource, but does not show how significant forests are relative to the country’s size or how intensively the land is forested.

Forest area as percent of land area is given in Figure 4. Finland and Slovenia have the highest percentage of forested land, Norway, Poland and France have around 30%, while Ireland has around 10%.

Figure 4: Forest area as percent of land area. Source: Eurostat - Area of wooded land (FAO) [for_area] (Eurostat 2026) and total land area for each country.

Volume of timber

The volume of timber in Europe represents the total growing stock contained in standing trees and reflects the long-term development of forest resources across the continent. It is a key indicator of forest productivity, management intensity and the balance between growth and harvesting. The distribution of timber volume varies widely between countries, influenced by forest area, species composition, age structure and site conditions.

Monitoring timber volume is essential for assessing the sustainability of forest use, evaluating the potential of the wood supply, and understanding forests' role in carbon storage and climate mitigation at both national and European scales.

The volume of timber in forests' growing stock (Figure 5A) shows an increasing trend in France, while it appears to level off in the other countries. It is highest in France, followed by Poland and Finland. The current volume in Norway is approximately 1 185 million m³, while in Slovenia it is approximately 380 million m³, and in Ireland it is approximately 145 million m³.

The volume of timber in the growing stock of other wooded land (Figure 5B) has increased in Norway and Finland since 1990, while declining in Slovenia. Currently, it is highest in Norway, followed by Finland. For Slovenia, the volume is currently slightly below 1 million m³, whereas 0 is recorded in the Eurostat database for Poland, no data were provided for France and Ireland.

Figure 5: Volume of timber, in thousand cubic metres, 1990-2025. A: growing stock of forests, B: growing stock of other wooded land. Please note the different scales on the two figures. Source: Eurostat - Volume of timber (FAO) [for_vol] (Eurostat 2026).

Type of forest

Table 4 presents forest growing stock, disaggregated by forest origin (naturally regenerating, planted, plantation forests and other planted forests) for the six European countries. The composition of forest growing stock by origin is relevant for understanding carbon storage, and potential trade-offs between production and ecological functions. In addition, the type of forest management influences timber characteristics, including variation in age structure, species mix, growth rate, stem quality, supply predictability, rotation length, and management.

Here and in the following: reported timber volumes can be given above (over) or below (under) bark, as bark inclusion varies by measurement conventions, reporting standards and intended use of the data.

Table 5: Forest characteristics, million m³ over bark, in 2025 for all countries. Source: FAO (2025).

	Naturally regenerating forest	...of which primary forest	Planted forest	...of which plantation forest	...of which introduced species	...of which other planted forest	Total
FR	15 439.00	-	2 356.00	-	-	2 356.00	17 795.00
FI	14707.05	602.99	7 835.95	29.31	29.31	7 806.64	22 543.00
PL	2 088.90	-	7 406.10	3.40	0.15	7 402.70	9 495.00
NO	11 995.53	224.54	113.11	113.1	85.00	0.00	12 108.64
SI	1 174.03	108.27	69.52	31.35	31.35	38.14	1 243.55
IE	117.33	0.00	715.52	715.52	506.70	0.00	832.85

Net annual increment

Net annual increment (NAI) describes the yearly biological growth of the forest, measured as the increase in the volume of living trees after subtracting natural losses such as mortality. It represents the net addition to growing stock that occurs independently of harvesting. It reflects how rapidly forest resources are renewed and provides a scientific basis for assessing the balance between growth and harvest. European forest statistics and international reporting frameworks rely on increment data to evaluate sustainable forest management, carbon sequestration potential, and the long-term capacity of forests to supply timber and other ecosystem services.

One way to present NAI is as the total volume of wood that forests gain each year from biological growth. It expresses national-level productivity in absolute terms and the total resource availability for wood supply. The NAI in thousand cubic metres (Figure 6A) is relatively stable across all countries from 1990 to 2015 but increases in Finland from 1990 to 2010. Finland has the highest NAI, followed by France, Norway, Slovenia and Ireland. No data were available for Poland.

Another way to illustrate NAI is in cubic metres per hectare in forest available for wood supply (FAWS), i.e., the part of the forest where harvesting is legally/economically possible (Figure 6B). FAWS excludes protected forests, steep slopes, conservation areas and urban forests. The highest NAI in cubic metres per hectare in FAWS are found in Ireland, followed by Slovenia, France, Finland and Norway. Ireland's high NAI per hectare in FAWS is most likely explained by productive site conditions, species composition dominated by fast-growing conifers, and management practices that maximise growth on harvestable forest land. The trend is generally relatively stable across all countries from 2010 to 2015, but it is increasing in Slovenia. When comparing Figure 6A and Figure 6B, we see that the between-country contribution shifts significantly.

The ratio of fellings to NAI is a key measure of sustainable wood use, ensuring that harvest levels do not exceed biological growth. When looking at fellings as a percent of NAI (Figure 6C), it is increasing for all countries from 2010 to 2015. Finland has the highest fellings as a percent of NAI, followed by Ireland, Slovenia, France and Norway. No data were available from Poland. Briefly, a low ratio is beneficial for carbon storage and biodiversity but may reduce forest resilience and lead to overly old stands. A moderate ratio is often considered sustainable and efficient in managed forests. If the ratio is >1, the country is over-harvesting. Hence, none of the six countries is overharvesting based on this criterion.

Figure 6: A: Net annual increment (NAI) over bark, in thousand cubic metres, B: NAI over bark, in cubic metres per hectare in forest available for wood supply (FAWS), C: Fellingings as a percent of NAI. Data for Poland was not available. Source: Forest Europe (2020).

3.2. Growing stock composition

The ten most common wood species and their volumes (in cubic metres) are listed for the six countries (FAO, 2020). In addition, the five most frequently introduced species are ranked in terms of volume.

Across the six countries, forest composition is strongly dominated by a small number of widespread European species, while introduced species play highly variable roles, ranging from negligible to dominant.

Native species

Across all countries, the native growing stock is concentrated in a handful of species with broad ecological ranges. Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) are consistently among the top species in France, Finland, Poland, Norway and Slovenia, reflecting their ecological flexibility and economic importance. European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is a leading hardwood species in France, Poland and Slovenia. Regionally characteristic hardwoods (oaks, birches, alder, aspen) appear within each country's top ten, but with smaller volumes than conifers in northern and central Europe. Overall, native species lists show high consistency across countries, with variation mainly driven by latitude (e.g., birch and aspen in the north, oak, chestnut and hornbeam in central Europe).

Introduced species

Introduced wood species refer to non-native trees deliberately planted to improve productivity, resilience, or economic value of forests. In this report, we follow FAO (2025) for the definition of introduced species. The contribution of introduced species to the national growing stock ranges from substantial to almost zero. France and Ireland have the highest volumes of introduced species. France is dominated by Douglas fir (*Pseudotsuga menziesii*), while Ireland is overwhelmingly dominated by Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis*), reflecting plantation-based forestry. Norway has moderate shares, with Sitka spruce the largest non-native species, followed by smaller volumes of larch, fir, and lodgepole pine. Finland has only very small volumes of introduced species; larches and *Pinus contorta* appear, but total volumes remain negligible. Slovenia reports no introduced species in growing stock. This geographical gradient reflects differences in forest policy, plantation history and ecological suitability for fast-growing non-native conifers.

Regional patterns

Some regional patterns were identified:

- Northern Europe (Finland, Norway): Conifer-dominated forests, largely native, with a small introduced component.
- Western Europe (France, Ireland): More diversified species mix overall, including significant plantation forestry with introduced conifers.
- Eastern and southern Europe (Poland, Slovenia): Mixed broadleaf-conifer forests with minimal or no introduced species.

Table 6: Growing stock composition, France, million m³ over bark, 2020. * = hardwood species. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Sessile oak*	<i>Quercus sessiflora</i>	343.59	11.68
#2	Pedunculate oak*	<i>Quercus robur</i>	338.09	11.49
#3	European beech*	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	308.05	10.47
#4	European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	229.15	7.79
#5	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	196.23	6.67
#6	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	154.13	5.24
#7	Maritime pine	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	154.10	5.24
#8	Sweet chestnut*	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	139.92	4.76
#9	European hornbeam*	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	125.68	4.27
#10	Downy oak*	<i>Quercus pubescens</i>	119.13	4.05
Remaining native tree species			539.95	18.35
*Total volume hardwood species			1374.46	46.72
Total volume			2 648.02	90.01
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Douglas fir	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	143.89	4.89
#2	-	<i>Pinus nigra nigra</i>	44.26	1.50
#3	Poplar*	<i>Populus sp.</i>	34.63	1.18
#4	Black locust*	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	34.33	1.17
#5	Sitka spruce	<i>Picea sitchensis</i>	8.71	0.30
Remaining introduced tree species			27.92	0.95
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			68.96	2.35
Total volume of introduced tree species			293.74	9.99
Total growing stock			2 941.76	

Table 7: Growing stock composition, Finland, million m³ over bark, 2020. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	1 273.14	50.15
#2	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	760.95	29.97
#3	Downy birch*	<i>Betula pubescens</i>	289.97	11.42
#4	Silver birch*	<i>Betula pendula</i>	121.06	5.00
#5	European aspen*	<i>Populus tremula</i>	40.81	1.75
#6	Grey alder*	<i>Alnus incana</i>	17.16	0.64
#7	Black alder*	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	6.97	0.31
#8	Goat willow*	<i>Salix caprea</i>	6.88	0.28
#9	Rowan/European mountain-ash*	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	6.88	0.26
#10	European bird cherry*	<i>Prunus padus</i>	0.70	0.03
Remaining native tree species			0.95	0.04
Total volume hardwood species			490.43	19.69
Total volume			2 446.04	99.87
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	European larch	<i>Larix decidua</i>	2.36	0.09
#2	Contorta pine	<i>Pinus contorta</i>	0.43	0.02
#3	Swiss pine	<i>Pinus cembra</i>	0.10	0.00
#4	European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	0.09	0.00
#5	Thuja	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	0.00	0.00
Remaining introduced tree species			0.38	0.01
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			0.00	0.00
Total volume of introduced tree species			3.36	0.13
Total growing stock			2 538.64	

Table 8: Growing stock composition, Poland, million m³ over bark, 2021. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	1 493.60	55.77
#2	Pedunculate oak, sessile oak*	<i>Quercus robur</i> , <i>Q. petraea</i>	216.21	8.07
#3	European beech*	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	193.44	7.22
#4	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	155.11	5.79
#5	Silver birch*	<i>Betula pendula</i>	145.29	5.42
#6	Black alder*	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	134.01	5.00
#7	European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	123.40	4.61
#8	European larch	<i>Larix decidua</i>	45.78	1,71
#9	European hornbeam*	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	37.37	1.40
#10	European aspen*	<i>Populus tremula</i>	26.08	0.97
Remaining native tree species			85.32	3.19
Total volume hardwood species			752.40	28.08
Total volume			2 655.61	99.15
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Red oak*	<i>Quercus rubra</i>	9.37	0.35
#2	Black locust	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	7.14	0.27
#3	Douglas fir	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	2.20	0.08
#4	Black cherry*	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	1.96	0.07
#5	Austrian pine	<i>Pinus nigra</i>	0.72	0.03
Remaining introduced tree species			1.37	0.05
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			11.33	0.42
Total volume of introduced tree species			22.76	0.85
Total growing stock			2 678.37	

Table 9: Growing stock composition, Norway, million m³ over bark, 2020. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	490.59	41.43
#2	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	350.00	29.56
#3	Downy birch*	<i>Betula pubescens</i>	192.55	16.26
#4	Grey alder*	<i>Alnus incana</i>	21.16	1.79
#5	European aspen*	<i>Populus tremula</i>	20.99	1.77
#6	Silver birch*	<i>Betula pendula</i>	13.72	1.16
#7	Goat willow*	<i>Salix caprea</i>	11.93	1.01
#8	Rowan/European mountain ash*	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	11.78	0.99
#9	Pedunculate oak*	<i>Quercus robur</i>	10.64	0.90
#10	Black alder*	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	2.78	0.23
Remaining native tree species			42.04	3.55
Total volume hardwood species			285.55	24.11
Total volume			1 168.18	98.65
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Sitka spruce	<i>Picea sitchensis</i>	10.93	0.92
#2	Contorta pine	<i>Pinus contorta</i>	1.49	0.13
#3	European silver fir (etc.)	<i>Abies alba</i>	1.46	0.12
#4	Larch	<i>Larix spp.</i>	1.05	0.09
#5	Sycamore	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	0.72	0.06
Remaining introduced tree species			0.29	0.02
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			0.00	0.00
Total volume of introduced tree species			15.94	1.35
Total growing stock			1 184.12	

Table 10: Growing stock composition, Slovenia, million m³ over bark, 2021. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Common beech*	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	115.38	30.56
#2	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	111.09	29.43
#3	European silver fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	30.26	8.02
#4	Sessile oak*	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	18.37	4.87
#5	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	15.91	4.21
#6	Sycamore maple*	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	13.63	3.61
#7	European hornbeam*	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	9.91	2.63
#8	European larch	<i>Larix decidua</i>	6.15	1.63
#9	Chestnut*	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	5.77	1.53
#10	Hop hornbeam*	<i>Ostrya carpinifolia</i>	5.33	1.41
Remaining native tree species			45.70	12.11
Total volume hardwood species			168.39	44.61
Total volume			377.50	100.00
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1- #5	-	-	-	-
Remaining introduced tree species			-	-
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			-	-
Total volume of introduced tree species			-	-
Total growing stock			377.50	

Table 11: Growing stock composition, Ireland, million m³ over bark, 2022. Source: FAO (2025).

	Common name	Scientific name	Million m ³ over bark	% of total
Native species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	European ash*	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	4.55	3.10
#2	Downy birch*	<i>Betula pubescens</i>	3.44	2.34
#3	Goat willow*	<i>Salix caprea</i>	2.75	1.87
#4	Pedunculate oak*	<i>Quercus robur</i>	2.67	1.82
#5	Black alder*	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	2.20	1.5
#6	Sessile oak*	<i>Quercus petraea</i>	2.05	1.4
#7	Scots pine	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	1.49	1.02
#8	Silver birch*	<i>Betula pendula</i>	1.44	0.98
#9	European holly*	<i>Ilex aquifolium</i>	0.52	0.35
#10	Common hazel*	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	0.49	0.33
Remaining native tree species			0.51	0.35
Total volume hardwood species			20.11	13.69
Total volume			22.11	15.07
Introduced species ranked in terms of volume				
#1	Sitka spruce	<i>Picea sitchensis</i>	88.31	60.19
#2	Lodgepole pine	<i>Pinus contorta</i>	11.60	7.91
#3	Norway spruce	<i>Picea abies</i>	6.19	4.22
#4	Japanese larch	<i>Larix kaempferi</i>	5.38	3.67
#5	Common beech*	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	3.63	2.47
Remaining introduced tree species			9.50	6.47
Total volume of introduced hardwood species			3.63	2.47
Total volume of introduced tree species			124.61	84.93
Total growing stock			146.72	

Forest disturbances

Table 11 presents reported forest disturbances, i.e. causes of damaged wood, by type and country. While the FAO provides comprehensive globally harmonised dataset on forest disturbances, the reported data are unlikely to be fully complete. Disturbance reporting relies largely on national self-reporting, and smaller-scale forest disturbances are difficult to measure. Hence, countries are likely to differ in monitoring capacity. As a result, forest disturbances are likely under-reported. More details about damaged wood are found in the report ‘Characteristics of underutilised wood stock’ by Nanda et al. (2025).

Table 12: Disturbance, volumes in 1 000 ha, from 2020* or 2022. Source: FAO (2025).

	Insects	Diseases	Severe weather events	Other
France	2.40	0.63	1.15	1.83
Finland*	7.00	73.00	111.00	175.00

Poland	-	-	109.10	-
Norway*	79.0.	16.0.	109.00	52.00
Slovenia	0.92	0.39	0.40	0.31
Ireland	-	0.31	-	-

Figure 7 gives an overview of the area affected by forest fires in the six European countries. The FAO data are based on national self-reporting. At first glance, the areas affected by fire in France appear similar for total land area and forest area; however, total area is consistently larger than forest area in all years, even if the difference is small in some years. According to EFI (2026), burnt areas in the EU surpassed 1 million hectares in 2025, twice the area lost in 2024, and the highest level recorded since 2006. Extreme wildfires are becoming more frequent due to climate change and land-use shifts such as land abandonment, which increase fuel loads and extend the fire season beyond its traditionally summer-centred period into early spring to late autumn. Risk is also rising in traditionally low-risk regions of Central and Northern Europe, and emerging studies indicate that fire-related mortality may be underestimated by up to 93%.

Figure 7: Area affected by fire, volumes in 1 000 ha. A: Total area, B: Forest area. Source: FAO (2025).

3.3. Environmental functions

Protected forest

Data on protected forests are recorded every fifth year by Eurostat (Figure 8), and the time series are more or less complete from 1990 to 2015 for all countries. Further, data for Norway are not available in Eurostat, and for some areas, neither for Ireland. Figure 8 illustrates the total ‘protected area’ and the protected area linked to ‘biodiversity’ and ‘landscape features’. Further, the protected area is given for both ‘forest and other wooded’ land and ‘forest’. Generally, the data coverage for protected areas is limited and heterogeneous. This might partly reflect the methodological complexity of quantifying ecological attributes and, potentially, in some contexts, the historical emphasis on production-oriented statistics. The trends are relatively stable for all countries and protected area types. Generally, the highest areas are found in France, followed by Finland, Poland, Slovenia and Ireland.

Although protected forests are primarily designated for conservation and are generally excluded from commercial harvesting, limited management interventions may still occur, such as pruning, removal of hazardous trees, sanitation felling, or ecological restoration, depending on protection category and national regulations. Consequently, small amounts of wood may be generated, but management objectives and allowable interventions differ across countries and protection types, with conservation goals consistently taking precedence over timber production.

Protective functions

Protective functions of forests in Europe include ways forests help stabilise the environment and reduce natural hazards and are recorded every fifth year by Eurostat (Figure 9). They include protecting soil and water by reducing erosion, regulating water flows and safeguarding drinking-water resources and riverbanks—functions especially important in erosion-prone and mountainous regions. Forests also protect infrastructure such as roads, railways and settlements from avalanches, landslides and rockfall, and some countries legally designate forest areas specifically for these purposes. Protective functions are becoming more important as climate change increases the frequency of extreme weather events and heightens risks such as erosion, avalanches and slope instability. Trends are relatively stable across all countries and areas of protective function types but show an increasing trend in Poland. The areas are also the highest for Poland. It is worth noting that for some areas, data are available only for Poland, and none are available for Norway or Ireland.

Figure 8: Protected forest, in thousand hectares, 1990-2015, incl. protected area, protected area - biodiversity, protected area - landscape features, for forest and other wooded land and for forest. No data are available for Norway in Eurostat. Source: Eurostat - Protected forests [for_protect] (Eurostat 2026).

Figure 9: Protective functions of forests, in thousand hectares, 1990-2015, incl. area with a protective function, area protecting soil and area protecting infrastructure, for forest and other wooded land and for forest. No data are available for Norway and Ireland in Eurostat. Source: Eurostat - Protective functions of forests [for_profnc] (Eurostat 2026).

Carbon stock

Table 12 provides an overview of carbon stocks in above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, dead wood, litter, soil, and total biomass. This overview highlights that forest carbon storage extends well beyond above-ground biomass. Note that all carbon pools are essential, as a substantial share of forest carbon is stored outside living biomass and these pools respond differently to disturbance, management and climate change. The highest total stock is found in France, followed by Poland, Finland, Norway, Slovenia and Ireland. Based on these data, the largest contribution is from forest soils, followed by above-ground biomass, below-ground biomass, litter, and dead wood.

Table 13: Carbon stock, tonnes/ha, in 2025. Source: FAO (2025).

	C in above-ground biomass	C in below-ground biomass	C in dead wood	C in litter	Soil C
France	1 104.62	316.03	168.16	-	-
Finland	688.69	199.51	18.26	253.83	3 807.06
Poland	731.39	146.28	51.82	-	-
Norway	31.27	8.35	1.37	-	-
Slovenia	108.39	24.12	5.01	5.60	98.50
Ireland	58.68	12.51	18.66	12.78	313.32

Sustainable forest management policies and legislation

Understanding the presence of policies, legislation, stakeholder participation platforms and traceability systems is essential for assessing policy coherence and implementation capacity for sustainable forest management. These elements underpin transparency, accountability, and stakeholder engagement along the forest value chain. Table 13 shows that all six countries have national policies and legislation supporting sustainable forest management (SFM). Sub-national arrangements are common in France and Finland (policies, stakeholder platforms, and traceability), Slovenia (policies, stakeholder platforms), while the other countries mainly report only national-level instruments, and Poland lacks a national stakeholder participation platform.

Table 14: Policies, legislation and national platform for stakeholder participation in forest policy, 1 00 ha. Sustainable Forest Management = SFM. Source: FAO (2025).

	Policies supporting SFM		Legislations and regulations supporting SFM		Platform that promotes or allows for stakeholder participation in forest policy development		Traceability system(s) for wood products	
	National	Sub-national	National	Sub-national	National	Sub-national	National	Sub-national
France	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Finland	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Poland	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	no
Norway	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no
Slovenia	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no
Ireland	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no

Sustainable Development Goal 15

Sustainable Development Goal 15 focuses on protecting, restoring, and sustainably managing terrestrial ecosystems, including forests, wetlands, mountains, and drylands, to halt biodiversity loss and reverse land degradation. It emphasises the need to combat deforestation and desertification, safeguard natural habitats, and ensure the long-term health of ecosystems essential to human well-being. Table 14 summarises the contributions of the six countries to SDG 15.1.1 and 15.1.2.

Table 15: Sustainable Development Goal 15, France. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	27.92	29.99	30.75	31.68	31.95	32.22	32.48	32.75	33.02
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	0.72	0.50	0.60	0.51	0.60	0.56			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	112.31	124.00	129.60	129.95	130.12	130.28	130.44	130.60	130.76
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas			22.73	23.70	23.82	23.94	24.07	24.19	24.31
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	38.49	42.60	45.36	47.71	47.77	47.82	47.87	47.93	47.98
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	1.1	3985.6	5117.9	8035.0	8215.1	8218.2	8017.7	8035.2	

Table 16: Sustainable Development Goal 15, Finland. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	73.69	73.19	73.74	74.17	74.24	74.24	74.24	74.24	74.24
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	-0.09	0.15	0.12	0.02	0.03	0.07			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	49.14	53.64	59.77	61.09	61.08	61.08	61.07	61.07	61.06
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas	12.02	13.26	13.91	14.53	14.57	14.62	14.66	14.71	14.75
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	100.00	99.26	100.00	100.00	100.62	100.64	100.66	100.68	100.00
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	21910.0	22367.2	20796.6	17614.1	16571.8	17744.5	18161.4	18082.2	

Table 17: Sustainable Development Goal 15, Poland. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	29.58	30.46	30.77	30.92	30.93	30.96	30.97	30.99	31.00
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	0.29	0.19	0.09	0.07	0.24	0.08			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	106.87	145.76	155.43	162.32	162.63	162.95	163.26	163.58	163.89
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas	2.95	3.18	33.65	33.78	33.81	33.83	33.86	33.89	33.92
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	89.81	91.68	94.80	97.52	97.73	97.94	98.16	98.37	98.59
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	1974.0	6977.6	6694.1	7407.0	7320.8	7261.2	7169.1	7372.4	

Table 18: Sustainable Development Goal 15, Norway. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	40.09	39.93	39.89	39.86	38.54	37.21	35.89	34.56	33.24
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	-0.04	-0.03	-0.02	-0.02	-0.03	-0.02			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	48.16	56.99	60.74	62.47	62.49	62.50	62.51	62.52	62.54
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas	2.21	3.45	4.21	5.01	5.17	5.33	5.49	5.65	5.81
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	39.08	30.79	45.55	56.42	56.58	56.74	56.90	57.06	57.22
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	5600.0	9236.8	9120.6	9218.4	7381.8	7380.9	7390.2	7351.5	7256.5

Table 19: Sustainable Development Goal 15, Slovenia. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	61.22	61.90	61.96	61.77	61.77	61.77	61.77	61.76	61.76
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	0.11	0.02	-0.07	0.00	0.06	-0.04			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	204.23	238.20	231.66	229.69	229.87	230.06	230.24	230.43	230.61
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas	10.85	19.01	20.59	19.59	22.94	26.28	29.63	32.97	36.32
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	98.80	99.92	100.00	99.67	99.66	99.66	99.65	99.65	99.64
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	0.0	0.0	212.1	297.1	296.6	297.3	301.1	300.9	

Table 20: Sustainable Development Goal 15, Ireland. Global Forest Resources Assessment 2025.

SDG Indicator 15.1.1 Forest area as proportion of total land area									
Indicator	Percent								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area as proportion of total land area	9.15	10.46	10.95	11.52	11.63	11.74	11.86	11.97	12.09
SDG Indicator 15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management									
Sub-Indicator 1	Percent								
	2000-2010	2010-2015	2015-2020	2020-2025	2005-2015	2015-2025			
Annual forest area change rate	1.34	0.93	1.00	0.98	1.12	0.99			
Sub-Indicator 2	Forest biomass (tonnes/ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Above-ground biomass stock in forest	87.36	103.85	115.53	122.62	121.57	120.52	119.46	118.41	117.36
Sub-Indicator 3	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area located within legally established protected areas	18.50	18.77	18.83	18.93	19.03	19.13	19.24	19.34	18.50
Sub-Indicator 4	Percent (2015 forest area baseline)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Proportion of forest area under long-term forest management plan	64.24	69.79	71.45	73.69	74.33	74.97	75.60	76.24	76.88
Sub-Indicator 5	Forest area (1000 ha)								
	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Forest area under independently verified forest management certification schemes	0.0	446.5	449.6	448.1	446.7	446.7	446.9	446.9	-

3.4. Roundwood removals

Roundwood removals are the volume of timber harvested from forests, including both industrial roundwood and wood used for energy. They constitute a key indicator of forest utilisation and link forest resources to economic activity in sectors such as construction, manufacturing, and energy production.

Trends in roundwood removals reflect a combination of biological potential, management practices, market demand and policy conditions. Harvest levels are influenced by forest growth, age structure, accessibility and ownership patterns, as well as by national regulations and sustainability objectives. As such, roundwood removals provide valuable insight into how forests are managed and mobilised across regions and over time.

From a sustainability perspective, roundwood removals are commonly assessed against forest growth to determine whether harvesting remains within long-term ecological limits (ref. section ‘Net annual increment’). Monitoring removals is also essential for understanding forests’ contributions to carbon balances, renewable material supply and the bioeconomy. In the WoodStock project quantification of roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment gives a baseline for current wood utilisation in the six case countries. Some of the assortments include underutilised wood resources and are commented on for each category.

In European forest statistics (e.g., Eurostat, FAOSTAT), roundwood removals serve as a harmonised metric that enables cross-country comparisons and supports policy analysis on forest management, climate mitigation, and resource efficiency. All data in this chapter is collected from the Eurostat database and reflects the time series available for different

countries and products. Generally, data are reported annually, but some of the time series have some gaps.

Roundwood is the timber that is harvested. The subcategories are listed in Table 1.

Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment

Roundwood (in the rough)

Definition: “All roundwood felled or otherwise harvested and removed. It comprises all wood obtained from removals, i.e. the quantities removed from forests and from trees outside the forest, including wood recovered from natural, felling and logging losses during the period, calendar year or forest year. It includes all wood removed with or without bark, including wood removed in its round form, or split, roughly squared or in other form (e.g. branches, roots, stumps and burls (where these are harvested) and wood that is roughly shaped or pointed. It is an aggregate comprising wood fuel, including wood for charcoal and industrial roundwood (wood in the rough). It is reported in cubic metres solid volume under bark (i.e. excluding bark).” JFSQ (2023).

Under the JFSQ definition, roundwood includes all wood that is felled or otherwise harvested and removed, regardless of its condition. This explicitly covers wood recovered from natural losses, such as storm-damaged, insect-damaged or otherwise deteriorated trees, as long as the material is removed from the forest and recorded as a removal. Thus, damaged wood is included in roundwood statistics when it is salvaged or collected. Across the three case countries, branches and tops may be harvested to a limited extent, mainly for bioenergy, while stumps, roots and burls are rarely harvested and, where allowed, are subject to strict environmental constraints.

Total roundwood removals (Figure 10A) are currently highest in Finland, followed by France and Poland. Finland and Poland have an increasing trend, while France has a decreasing trend. Removals in Norway are quite stable at approximately 10 million m³, while Slovenia and Ireland are below 5 million m³.

The proportion of non-coniferous roundwood removals (in the following termed hardwood) tends to decrease in France and slightly increase in Finland. The volumes are highest in France, followed by Finland and Poland. The hardwood roundwood removals (Figure 10B) from Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are generally stable and below 2 million m³.

Figure 10: Roundwood 1992-2024, under bark, in thousand cubic metres. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Wood fuel

Definition: “Roundwood that will be used as fuel for purposes such as cooking, heating or power production. It includes wood harvested from main stems, branches and other parts of trees (where these are harvested for fuel), round or split, and wood that will be used for the production of charcoal (e.g. in pit kilns and portable ovens), wood pellets and other agglomerates. The volume of roundwood used in charcoal production is estimated by using a factor of 6.0 to convert from the weight (mt) of charcoal produced to the solid volume (m³) of roundwood used in production. It also includes wood chips to be used for fuel that are made directly (i.e. in the forest) from roundwood. It excludes wood charcoal, pellets and other agglomerates.” JFSQ (2023).

Total wood fuel removals (Figure 11A) are highest in France, followed by Finland and Poland. Finland and Poland show a slight upward trend, while France has been quite stable over the last decade. Removals in Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are generally stable and below 2.5 million m³.

The proportion of hardwood fuel removals (Figure 11B) is highest in France, followed by Finland and Poland. The hardwood timber contribution from Norway, Slovenia and Ireland is generally below 1.5 million m³. The trends are the same as for total fuelwood removals.

Figure 11: Fuelwood (including wood for charcoal) 1992-2024, under bark, in thousand cubic metres. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Industrial roundwood

Definition: “All roundwood except wood fuel. In the removal statistics, it represents the sum of sawlogs and veneer logs; pulpwood, round and split; and other industrial roundwood. It is reported in cubic metres solid volume under bark (i.e. excluding bark). The custom classification systems used by most countries do not allow the division of Industrial Roundwood trade statistics into the different end-use categories that have long been recognized in production statistics (i.e. sawlogs and veneer logs, pulpwood and other industrial roundwood). Thus, these components do not appear in the trade statistics.” JFSQ (2023).

Total industrial roundwood removals (Figure 12A) are highest in Finland, followed by Poland and France. Finland and Poland show an upward trend, while France shows a slight downward trend. Removals in Norway are quite stable at approximately 10 million m³, while Slovenia and Ireland are below 5 million m³.

The proportion of hardwood industrial roundwood removals (Figure 12B) is currently quite similar in France, Finland and Poland, quite stable and slightly below 10 million m³. The hardwood industrial roundwood removals from Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are generally below 1 million m³.

Figure 12: Industrial roundwood 1992-2024, under bark, in thousand cubic metres. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Please note the different scale on the y-axis in A and B. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Sawlogs and veneer logs

Definition: “Roundwood that will be sawn (or chipped) lengthways for the manufacture of sawnwood or railway sleepers (ties) or used for the production of veneer (mainly by peeling or slicing). It includes roundwood (whether or not it is roughly squared) that will be used for these purposes; shingle bolts and stave bolts; match billets and other special types of roundwood (e.g. burls and roots, etc.) used for veneer production.” JFSQ (2023).

Total sawlog and veneer log removals (Figure 13A) are highest in Finland, followed by Poland and France. Finland and Poland show an upward trend, while France shows a slight downward trend. Removals in Norway are quite stable at approximately 10 million m³, while Slovenia and Ireland are below 5 million m³.

The proportion of hardwood sawlogs and veneer logs removals (Figure 13B) is highest in France, followed by Poland and Finland. The hardwood industrial roundwood removals from Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are below 0.5 million m³. The trend is relatively stable in all countries.

Figure 13: Sawlogs and veneer logs 1992-2024, under bark, in thousand cubic metres. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Pulpwood, round and split

Definition: “Roundwood that will be used for the production of pulp, particle board, oriented strand board (OSB) or fibreboard. It includes roundwood (with or without bark) that will be used for these purposes in its round form or as splitwood or wood chips made directly (i.e. in the forest) from roundwood.” JFSQ (2023).

Total pulpwood, round and split removals (Figure 14A) are highest in Finland, followed by Poland and France. Finland and Poland show an upward trend, while France shows a relatively stable trend. Removals in Norway are quite stable at approximately 5 million m³, while Slovenia and Ireland are generally below 1 million m³.

The proportion of hardwood pulpwood, round and split removals (Figure 14B) is highest in Finland, followed by Poland and France. The hardwood pulpwood, round and split removals from Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are below 0.5 million m³. The trend is relatively stable in all countries.

Figure 14: Pulpwood, round and split 1992-2024, under bark, in cubic metres. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Other industrial roundwood

Definition: “Industrial roundwood (wood in the rough) other than sawlogs, veneer logs and/or pulpwood. It includes roundwood used for poles, piling, posts, fencing, pitprops, shingles and shakes, wood wool, tanning, distillation, shiitake mushroom growing and match blocks, etc.” JFSQ (2023).

Total other industrial roundwood removals (Figure 15A) are highest in Poland, followed by France. Poland shows a downward trend, while France shows a relatively stable trend. For the other countries, current removals of other industrial roundwood are below 0.2 million m³, or zero (Finland).

The proportion of hardwood industrial roundwood removals (Figure 15B) is currently highest in France. For the other countries, the removals are currently below 0.1 million m³.

Figure 15: Other industrial roundwood 1992-2024, under bark, in thousand cubic metres, A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals by type of wood and assortment [for_remov] (Eurostat 2026).

Roundwood removals by type of ownership

Disaggregating roundwood removals by ownership type provides insight into the structural and institutional drivers shaping harvesting patterns across Europe. Forest ownership strongly influences management practices, harvesting intensity, and decision-making timescales. Publicly owned forests are often managed with multiple objectives, including

biodiversity conservation, recreation, and long-term resource stewardship, alongside timber production. In contrast, privately owned forests may prioritise income generation and operational flexibility, while ownership fragmentation can affect harvesting efficiency and market participation. Analysing removals by ownership category, therefore, helps explain observed differences in harvesting behaviour and supply responses across countries and regions.

State ownership

Total roundwood removals with state ownership (Figure 16A) are highest in Poland and have been increasing since 2003. The remaining countries show a relatively stable trend. France and Finland are at the same level, around 5 million m³, while Norway, Slovenia and Ireland are lower.

The proportion of hardwood roundwood removals with state ownership (Figure 16B) is quite stable in all six countries. It is highest in Poland (nearly 10 million m³), followed by France (around 2 million m³). Low volumes are reported from Slovenia, Ireland, and Norway. No data has been reported for Finland since 2018.

Figure 16: State ownership, roundwood removals, under bark, in thousand cubic metres, 1992-2024. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals under bark by type of ownership [for_owner] (Eurostat 2026).

Other public ownership

Total roundwood removals with other public ownership (Figure 17A) are quite stable and in all countries and are highest in France (around 6 million m³), followed by Poland and Norway (around 600 000 m³). Slovenia is around 50 000 m³, while no data are available for Finland and Ireland.

The proportion of hardwood roundwood removals with other public ownership (Figure 17B) is highest in France (nearly 4 million m³) followed by Poland (around 300 000 m³). Small volumes are found in Slovenia and Norway, and no data are available for Ireland and Finland.

Figure 17: Other public ownership, roundwood removals, under bark, in thousand cubic metres, 1992-2024. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals under bark by type of ownership [for_owner] (Eurostat 2026).

Private ownership

Total roundwood removals with private ownership (Figure 18A) are highest in Finland, with an increasing trend, but no data is available since 2018. It is followed by France (around 40 million m³) and Norway (around 12 million m³), both with quite stable trends. Poland and Slovenia have less than 4 million m³, while Ireland has around 1 million m³.

The proportion of hardwood roundwood removals with private ownership (Figure 18B) currently shows quite stable trends and is highest in France (around 25 million m³) followed by Finland. The remaining countries have 1 million m³ or less.

Figure 18: Private ownership, roundwood removals, under bark, in thousand cubic metres, 1992-2024. A: all species, B: hardwood species. Source: Eurostat - Roundwood removals under bark by type of ownership [for_owner] (Eurostat 2026).

3.5. Economic aggregates of forestry

Output of forestry and connected secondary activities

In Eurostat’s forest accounts, output of forestry and related secondary activities denotes the total value of goods and services produced by the forestry and logging sector. It covers primary outputs such as timber and fuelwood, along with secondary activities such as forest management, logging support, and limited on-site processing. The indicator reflects the sector’s total economic value before deducting intermediate costs and forms part of the extended Economic Accounts for Forestry.

The highest output of forestry and connected secondary activities (Figure 19) was in France, followed closely by Poland (both around 8 000 M€) and then by Finland (close to 7 000 M€). All three countries have an upward trend. Norway, Slovenia and Ireland have a stable trend below 1 500 M€.

Figure 19: Economic aggregates of forestry, in million euros, output of forestry and connected secondary activities. Source: Eurostat - Economic aggregates of forestry [for_eco_cp] (Eurostat 2026).

Gross value added

Gross value added (GVA) in forestry shows how much the forestry and logging sector contributes to the economy after paying for the inputs it uses, such as fuel, services, equipment and materials. It is calculated as the value of what the sector produces minus these operating costs. GVA is an important international economic indicator and is closely linked to GDP, defined as total GVA plus taxes on products minus subsidies. In the EU, GVA highlights the real economic role of forest-based production.

Gross value added (Figure 20) is highest in Finland, currently closely followed by France (around 4 000 M€). Poland has around 2 500 M€. All three countries have an upward trend. Norway, Slovenia and Ireland have a stable trend below 1 000 M€.

Figure 20: Economic aggregates of forestry, in million euros, gross value added. Source: Eurostat - Economic aggregates of forestry [for_eco_cp] (Eurostat 2026).

Gender balance in employment

The gender balance in employment in forestry and logging is provided in Table 15. The highest employment is found in Poland, followed by France, Finland, Norway, Slovenia and Ireland. The highest proportion of female employment is in Norway, followed by Poland, France, Finland, and Slovenia. A more diverse workforce can help address labour shortages, expand skills, and make the forestry and logging sector more attractive and resilient.

Table 21: Employment in forestry and logging, 1 000 Full-Time Equivalent (FTE), 2015. Source: FAO (2020).

	Female	Male	Total
France	3.23 (11.4%)	25.02 (88.6%)	28.25
Finland	2.60 (10.7%)	21.70 (89.3%)	24.30
Poland	10.73 (14.2%)	65.10 (85.8%)	75.83
Norway	0.99 (17.2%)	4.78 (82.8%)	5.77
Slovenia	0.13 (0.13%)	3.5 (96.4%)	3.63
Ireland	-	-	2.34

4. Post-consumer wood

Post-consumer wood is a resource that is reused or recycled in Europe only to a limited degree. To understand how the resource can be utilised more effectively, data on generated quantities, origin and downstream treatment are crucial.

Post-consumer wood statistics are reported from the EU Member States, the candidate countries, and the EEA countries (Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway) to the Statistical Office of the European Communities (Eurostat, 2010). Here, data from all these countries are included, with a focus on the case countries Finland, Norway, Slovenia, Ireland, and France. The datasets on post-consumer wood cover waste generation and waste treatment. It is reported whether the waste generated originates from households or enterprises based on their economic activity number (NACE Rev. 2 activity). The waste generation dataset used in this report includes by-products, while the dataset for waste treatment includes all waste handled at waste management facilities in the reporting country, including imported waste (Eurostat, 2024a). The treatment categories as defined by the manual for the Implementation of Regulation (EC) No 2150/2002 on Waste Statistics (Eurostat, 2024b) are:

- Energy recovery: “incineration and co-incineration of waste in power stations and industrial facilities such as cement kilns so that the resultant energy can be used to generate heat or electricity”,
- Waste incineration: “main purpose of the incineration is the thermal treatment of waste in order to reduce the volume and the hazardousness of the waste”,
- Recycling: “waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes”,
- Backfilling: “non- hazardous waste is used for purposes of reclamation in excavated areas or for engineering purposes in landscaping”,

- Landfilling: “Deposit of landfills, including landfills for inert waste, non-hazardous waste and hazardous waste above ground, underground landfills, and use of waste as daily landfill cover”,
- Other forms of disposal: “land treatment (e.g. biodegradation of liquid or sludgy discards in soils, etc.), deep injection (e.g. injection of pumpable discards into wells, salt domes or naturally occurring repositories, etc.), deposit of waste in natural or engineered ponds, pits or lagoons or release into water bodies including sea-bed insertion”.

4.1. Post-consumer wood generation

The total amount of post-consumer wood generated in the European Union, the candidate countries and the EEA was 47 917 480 tons in 2020. Germany was the country generating the most post-consumer wood in total, with 12 131 000 tons in 2020 (Figure 21) and France generated the second most, while Finland was the country producing the most post-consumer wood per capita (565 kg/capita), and Belgium came second (Figure 22). Among the case countries, France and Finland are generating substantially more post-consumer wood than Poland, Norway, Ireland, and Slovenia. France and Finland generate 7 617 000 and 3 119 000 tons, while Poland, Norway, Ireland, and Slovenia generate 1 255 000, 818 000, 294 000, 91 000 tons, respectively. Although Finland by far generates the most post-consumer wood per capita, Norway also generates more than France, with 152 kg/capita compared to 114 kg/capita. Ireland, Slovenia, and Poland produce less with 60, 44, and 33 kg of post-consumer wood per capita.

Figure 21: Wood waste generation per country in Europe in 2020. In 1000 tonnes. Source: Eurostat -Generation of waste by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity [env_wasgen] (Eurostat, 2025a).

Figure 22: Post-consumer wood generation in Europe 2020. Kg per capita. Source: Eurostat - Generation of waste by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity (Eurostat, 2025a).

4.2. Post-consumer wood generation, by source

The highest amount of post-consumer wood comes from manufacturing industries, including wood manufacturing, sawmilling, and wood planing (Figure 23, European Commission, 2008). The sectors' dominance has been decreasing since 2004, and the construction sector and waste management industries (water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities) are becoming increasingly important. In the manual for the Implementation of Regulation (EC) No 2150/2002 on Waste Statistics, it is written that wood wastes are “wooden packaging, sawdust, shavings, cuttings, waste bark, cork and wood from production of pulp and paper, wood from construction and demolition of buildings, separately collected wood waste. They mainly originate from wood processing, pulp and paper industry and demolition of buildings but can occur in all economic activities in smaller quantities due to wooden packaging” (Eurostat, 2024b)

Figure 23: Generation of post-consumer wood in Europe from 2004 to 2022 [1000 tonnes], by NACE activity or households. Source: Eurostat - Generation of waste by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity (Eurostat, 2025a).

Most countries in Europe are dominated by post-consumer wood from *manufacturing industries*, and in Türkiye, Lichtenstein, Montenegro, Kosovo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Albania, more than 90% of the post-consumer wood originates from this industry. The case countries, Poland and Finland, generate 74% and 84% in the manufacturing industries. Oppositely, Slovenia and Malta are the only two countries with more than 60% post-consumer wood from *households*, and Iceland’s *water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities* generate 71% of the post-consumer wood. In the Netherlands, 54% of the post-consumer wood comes from the *construction industry*. The case countries, Norway, France, and Ireland, generate post-consumer wood from more mixed origins, but in Norway, it is interesting to note that only 13% comes from manufacturing industries.

Figure 24: Generation of post-consumer wood in 2022, grouped by country, all NACE activities plus households. Source: Eurostat - Generation of waste by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity (Eurostat, 2025a).

4.3. Downstream treatment of post-consumer wood

The percentage of non-hazardous post-consumer wood sent to energy recovery in Europe is stable at around 50%. Furthermore, about half is reported as recycled (Figure 25). Most of the post-consumer wood sent to recycling is used in the wood-based panel industry, and in 2017, 15% of the material used in this industry came from post-consumer wood (Avitabile et al., 2023). It mostly goes to particle board production, which, in theory, could be made from post-consumer wood and by-products only, but primary wood is still commonly used to produce particle boards. There is, however, limited data on reuse of wood products in Europe (Orfanidou et al., 2026)

Figure 25: Treatment of post-consumer wood in EU27 (from 2020). All treatment categories. Source: Eurostat - Treatment of waste by waste category, hazardousness and waste management operations [env_wastrt] (Eurostat, 2025b).

The rate of post-consumer wood that is landfilled, backfilled, incinerated or treated in another way is significantly smaller than the rate which is recycled or used for production of energy. The development of these smaller treatment categories is depicted in Figure 26. The incinerated and landfilled post-consumer wood decreased from 2010 to 2020, while from 2020 to 2022, the incineration rate increased slightly.

Figure 26: Treatment of post-consumer wood in EU 27 (from 2020) [1000 tonnes], including only the smallest treatment categories. The percentage is given as a ratio of all treatment categories. Source: Eurostat - Treatment of waste by waste category, hazardousness and waste management operations [env_wastrt] (Eurostat, 2025b).

In the case countries, Finland and Norway, the majority of the post-consumer wood is used for energy recovery (Figure 27). These countries facilitate waste incineration plants that send waste to heat recovery and have few wood-based panels manufactories adapted for post-consumer wood use. There is a dip in the amount of post-consumer wood managed in Finland from 2012 to 2014, and the amount stays relatively low until 2022, which could indicate that more post-consumer wood is sent to other countries for energy purposes. Although the amount of post-consumer wood treated in Finland is low today compared to 2010 and 2012, the total amount is substantially larger than in Norway, Slovenia, and Ireland. Most post-consumer wood is treated in France, and the amount has increased from 2012 to 2022. France is the country that treats the most post-consumer wood in the whole European Union (Figure 28) and recycles around half of it, although the recycling rate has gone down from 69% in 2010 to 51% in 2022. Poland and Ireland also recycle more than half of the post-consumer wood, and although the total post-consumer wood treated in Slovenia has decreased, a larger percentage of it has been recycled over the last two years.

Figure 27: Treatment of post-consumer wood in Finland, Norway, Slovenia, France, Ireland, and Poland (1000 tons). Note the different scale on the y-axis. Source: Eurostat - Treatment of waste by waste category, hazardousness and waste management operations [env_wastrt] (Eurostat, 2025b).

It is interesting to note that although Germany is the largest producer of post-consumer wood in Europe (Figure 21), France is treating the most (Figure 28). While all post-consumer wood treated in Germany is energy recovered, France recycles 51%. It is also worth noting that Italy recycles 82% of the treated post-consumer wood and treats the third most. This could indicate that countries with industries that recycle post-consumer wood receive wood from other countries where these industries do not exist.

Figure 28: Treatment of post-consumer wood in Europe [1000 tonnes]. Source: Eurostat - Treatment of waste by waste category, hazardousness and waste management operations [env_wastrt] (Eurostat, 2025b).

5. The European building stock - a summary

Wood elements in the building stock contribute to the storage of biogenic carbon and may be reused or recycled when buildings are demolished or renovated. The types and number of buildings and dwelling units in a region influence the amount of wood stored in the building stock. Therefore, a brief overview of the building stock in Europe follows. More in-depth information can be found in the WoodStock D3.2 report “*Material Intensities in the building stock*” by Gedde (2026).

According to the European Union Building Stock Observatory, the number of non-residential buildings in 2020 was 11.55 million buildings, and the number of residential buildings was 114 million, where 65% of the residential buildings were single-family buildings (European Union, 2020). The same source states that the total number of dwellings in residential buildings was 236 million in 2023, and half were single-family buildings. However, based on Eurostat, the total number of dwellings in 2021 was 184 717 733, of which 53% were in buildings with three or more dwellings and only 39% in one-dwelling buildings (Figure 29). It should be mentioned that one-dwelling buildings are not the same as single-family houses as single-family houses include both detached and semi-detached houses (terraced houses), while one-dwelling buildings are detached houses only (Dario Bottino Leone et al., 2023).

Figure 29: The number of dwellings in residential buildings, by type of building for EU27 (from 2020). Source: Eurostat - Dwellings by type of building, number of rooms or useful floor space and NUTS 3 region [cens_21dwbnr_r3] (Eurostat, 2025c).

In the case countries, most dwellings can be found in France (above 30 million dwellings) and Poland (above 12 million), and least in Slovenia (less than 1 million dwellings). In Ireland, 88% of dwellings are in one-dwelling buildings, the highest percentage in Europe. Finland and Poland have 62 and 56% of their dwellings in three or more dwelling buildings.

Figure 30: The number (left) and percentage (right) of dwellings in residential buildings, by type of building. Source: Eurostat - Dwellings by type of building, number of rooms or useful floor space and NUTS 3 region [cens_21dwbnr_r3] (Eurostat, 2025c)

Based on the material intensity data collected in the “Material Intensities in the building stock” report, it appears that wood use in small and large buildings is comparable. However, by differentiating the buildings by the main construction material, we see that the small wooden buildings, on average, contain more wood per square meter than the larger ones.

Figure 31: Material Intensity [kg/m²] of wood. Right: In small and large buildings. Left: In small and large buildings by the main construction material. Source: “Material Intensities in the building stock”.

The number of wooden buildings is a crucial factor for quantifying the amount of wood stored in the built environment, but this figure is not readily available in most countries. In Norway, the last survey of living conditions that included data on the wooden building stock is from 1967, which found that 91% of the smaller buildings were wooden, and 80% of the residential buildings in total (Statistics Norway, 1967). Data on the number of new wooden dwellings constructed in 2000 shows that 82% of the residential buildings were wooden. Similarly, about 80% of the detached houses in Finland are wooden (Nasiri et al., 2021). However, these percentages are likely much lower in France, Poland, Slovenia, and Ireland, where the tradition of building with wood is less prevalent than in Northern European countries. In Poland, the wooden construction percentage is rising, but it is still only 0.6% of the total (Mazur and Winkler, 2025). The percentage of new residential wooden construction in France is increasing as well, and was at 6.2% in 2022 (“Building with Wood,” n.d.). Moreover, a regulation that will be enforced in 2030 demands that 25% of public construction and renovation in France should come from bio-based and low-carbon materials (“Building with Wood,” n.d.). In Ireland, the increase has been even higher, from ca. 1% in the early 20th century (Sikkema et al., 2023) to around 24% of the total new build constructions in 2022 (Moreno et al., n.d.). Hence, there seems to be an increase in wood construction in Europe, but these resources will not be available for recycling or reuse for long because of long building lifetimes. At the same time, the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) includes the requirement that the life-cycle global warming potential must be calculated for all new buildings, promoting sustainable construction and carbon storage in buildings through wood construction (European Commission, 2025a). Additionally, the Construction Product Regulations (CPR) require documentation for products’ environmental sustainability performance and digital passports, which may promote wood materials and reuse (European Commission, 2025b). In a WoodStock context, underutilised wood resources could be used in these new constructions.

6. Conclusions

The report provides an overview of the forests, the forest resources, and the post-consumer wood in Europe with a focus on underutilised wood resources. A limited number of tree species dominate the growing stock, with conifers prevailing in northern and central Europe and broadleaved species more common further south.

There is a lot of data on the commonly used wood species, but little data on damaged wood and low-quality wood. Data on hardwood is also more limited than data on softwood, reflecting that softwood is the most common wood type in the industry. Post-consumer wood is reported in generated tons by source and downstream treatment. To utilise post-consumer wood in new products, information about the species and product types would be beneficial.

The forest sector is highly optimised and industrialised. Most by-products are utilised efficiently, either at the processing facilities as energy wood to run the operations or sold for other purposes. Using underutilised wood products demands industrial efficiency or high-quality niche products, and for the industry to plan for using new resources, information about the availability and quality of these is needed. A reason why there is limited information about damaged and low-quality wood could be that it is currently not used in high-quality applications, but for energy purposes, where quality information is not needed. Another reason is that annual volumes can vary significantly due to the randomness of severe weather events and/or insect damage.

Overall, the inventory provides a solid baseline for wood material availability in Europe. The study also demonstrates that parts of Europe's wood resources remain poorly documented. Improved reporting and stronger links between forest, processing, use and end-of-life stages are essential to support climate-smart construction, circular bioeconomy strategies and more efficient use of forest resources.

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